

Effect of Astaxanthin on Blood Factors and Chemical Composition of Carp *Cyprinus caprio*

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Abstract:

Astaxanthin dye was extracted from the Lobster shells to study its effect on the blood factors of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). mixture of organic solvents hexane and acetone (1:1, V/V) is used for Astaxanthin extraction. Extracted dye was added at 0.5, 0.10, and 0.15 mg/kg to four experimental diets that fed to common carp fingerling for 60 days. The chemical composition of the control and experimental diet protein, fat, ash, and moisture content was 42, 6.2, 7.5, 7.13% respectively. Blood samples Parameters observed that the highest values observed in fish-fed diets with 150 mg/kg in blood

factors PVC, BRC, and WRC were recorded at 36%, 1.45 106 mm³, 33.6 103 mm³, and 14 g/dl respectively compared to a control diet. It was concluded that supplementation of astaxanthin at 150 mg/kg increased the immune system in *C. carpio*. The scores for A, B, C, and D were 73%, 73.2%, 73.1%, and 73.1%, respectively. The results showed an increase in the protein, fat, and ash content were 18, 15, and 3% respectively, for fish fingerlings fed with astaxanthin at a rate of 0.15%.

Keywords: *Astaxanthin, blood factors, Cyprinus caprio, Chemical Composition, Lobster.*

Introduction

Aquatic organisms are rich sources of astaxanthin pigment, Lopster, and krill fish are also rich sources of this pigment. In numerous countries, this pigment is collected, dried, ground into a powder, and used in the food industry. It can also be obtained from *phaffia* yeast and *Haematococcus* algae through chemical synthesis. The highest level of astaxanthin in salmon is 26-38 mg/kg (Ranga, et al., 2014). This pigment plays an important role in protecting fish meat from the oxidation of its fatty acids. It is found either free or in a complex association with protein. (Astanthin-protein complex) Its functional properties are because of its presence in the free form in fats and its rapid and efficient transfer within the body (Wang, & Quinn, 1999). Sachindra, Bhaskar, & Mahendrakar, (2006) used

organic solvents to extract astaxanthin from shrimp shells and the use of a mixture of ethanol and isopropanol solvents gave a higher extraction yield. Astaxanthin is one of the most efficient carotenoids in controlling lipid oxidation and has two effects: the first is towards oxygen and the second is in scavenging free radicals, Using small concentrations of this dye gives a strong effect compared to vitamin E, which is added in concentrations of 20-100 ppm, and at the same time it is resistant to oxidation (Haifa, & Mazin, 2018). Some studies have confirmed that mixing this pigment extracted from algae with fish feed led to an increase in the immune system rates in mice (Capelli, & Gerald, 2013). In EFSA 2014, the dye extracted from shrimp shells was added to fish feed at a concentration of 0.01% and it was found that this percentage is safe for the consumer. This

study included add astaxanthin to fish feed and study its effect on chemical and physical properties of fish meat besides its effect on biological system in fish.

Materials and Methods

Fish Feeding

Healthy fingerlings of *C. carpio* at weight (20.99–21.85) g were procured from a commercial market in Baghdad/Iraq. Fish were adapted and then distributed randomly into duplicate glass tanks as 5 fish/ tank, at Baghdad University. Duplicate was maintained, A control and 3 experimental groups (B, C, D) were maintained. Fishes were fed with experimental diets 3 times a day (8, 12, 14 hours) for 60 days. Temperature, pH, and oxygen levels were measured, respectively.

Preparing Fish Feed

Four experimental diets were formed. The first treatment diet was without adding astaxanthin dye and was considered the control sample. Astaxanthin dye was added to the other experimental diets at different concentrations of 0.05%, 1%, and 0.15% and they are indicated by symbols (TA, TB, TC, TD) were formulated (table 1) as follows:

TA – Normal diet without any addition (control)

TB – Diet with astaxanthin 50mg/kg

TC – Diet with astaxanthin 100mg/kg

TD – Diet with astaxanthin 150mg/kg

Table 1. Formulation Composition of the Control Feed for Fish (*C. carpio*)

Composition	%
Fish powder	33
Soybean flower	16
Corn	42
Bran	6
Bro biotic	1
Vitamins ⁷	2

Table 2. Nutritional Composition of Control Carp Diet

Chemical Composition	%
protein	42
fat	6.2
ash	7.5
Moisture content	7.13

Extraction of Astaxanthin Pigment from Lobster Shells

Lobster waste was collected from Iraqi local markets and transported to the laboratory. The shells were scraped free of meat, washed under running water, and air-dried in the at room temperature. They were ground into powder, dried yield were After drying, store in polyethylene bags and stored at (-20C°) until use. The crude extracted Sachindra, Bhaskar, & Mahendrakar, (2006) by using a a mixture of organic solvents Hexane: Acetone (1:1) V: V. Astaxanthin was purified and centrifuged at 3000 rpm and evaporated to dryness (Harborne, 1973).

Preparing Blood Samples of Experimental Fish (*Cyprinus caprio*)

Blood samples were taken from fish for each treatment from the caudal vein by guage 3 ml. Samples were taken three times. at 0,30,50 days. Blood taken from the fish into a micro test tube containing a drop of heparin (anticoagulant) was poured and shaken gently until completely mixed blood and heparin (Gurien, Muntly, & Olaiazola, 2000). To measure the blood factors was According to providing company.

Determination of Packed Cell Volume (PVC) Value in Blood of Carp (*Cyprinus caprio*)

Collected blood from the capillary tube directly into a heparinized microhaematocrit tube long 75 mm, The inspection was carried out according to the instructions received from the company supplying the materials.

Determination of Red and White Cell Count in Blood of Carp (*Cyprinus caprio*)

Red blood cell count (RBCs x 106 /mm³) and (WBCs x 103 / mm³), Haemocytometer slide by

using commercial kits (Ranox company, Germany) according to the method described by (Zinkl, 1986).

Determination of Moisture, Protein, Fat and Ash Content

It was conducted according to –AOAC (1984).

Statistical Analysis

The statistical program SAS 2012 (2012) was used and the significant differences between the means were compared using the LSD. The level of significance was estimated at ($p < 0.05$).

Results and Discussion

Role of Astaxanthin on % PVC index in Carp

Figure 1. observed significant differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$). TD recorded 36.2

Figure 1. Effect of the Astaxanthin on % PVC Factor in Carp

Role of Astaxanthin on RBC and WBC Index in Blood of Carp

Figure 2. observed that (TD) which was fed with 150mg/kg astaxanthin, had the highest value in RBC after 60 days of feeding at $1.46 \times 10^6 / \text{mm}^3$ compared with TA which was fed with a normal diet without any astaxanthin supplement was the lowest value between the treatments $1.25 \times 10^6 / \text{mm}^3$ at the same period of feeding. B and C showed 1.28 and $1.37 \times 10^6 / \text{mm}^3$ values respectively. It was found that feeding mice

/100 ml blood compared with control treatment (A) was 31. /100ml, while values of PVC were 31, 32 / 100ml blood to B and C, respectively. Ranga, et al., (2014) reported. The effectiveness of this dye is estimated to be 100 times stronger than beta-carotene, as it performs the function of vitamin E A Swedish study showed that the dye astaxanthin has a high biological effectiveness in binding free radicals when feeding 40 healthy students who were divided into two groups. The first group was given astaxanthin in their food, taken from algae *Haemtococcus* while the second group was fed food devoid of astaxanthin. After six months of the experiment, there was a significant difference in the first group in blood tests and weight compared to the other group (Osterlie, & Liaan, 1999).

astaxanthin reduced the incidence of diabetes through a blood test taken from the liver (Capelli, & Gerald, 2013). Torrissen, (1986) was found that this dye is more effective than the control treatment. Salmon absorbs astaxanthin dye at a rate of 10-20 times that of other dyes (Torrissen, Hardy, & Shearer, 1989). A positive effect was found on the biochemical characteristics of trout blood in rainbow trout fed with diet supplemented by red yeast (*phaffia rodosynima*) containing astaxanthin.

Figure 2. Role of Astaxanthin on RBC Index 106 / mm³ in Carp

Figure 3 showed there was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between treatments, the highest value of WBC was in TD 33.9 10³ / mm³ after 60 days of feeding compared with TA which showed the lowest value 25 10³ / mm³, while T B and T C had values 26.0 and 28.5 10³ / mm³ respectively. Astaxanthin increased resistance of the immune system, These results agreed with Maede, et al., (2020). Amaninijad, et

al., (2009) reported that Carotenoids obtained from some algae increased the immune system in fish. Nakano, Tosa, & Takeuchi, (1995) also found this dye was more effective on blood factors. Carotenoids extracts in general, and astaxanthin in particular as an antioxidant, have received much attention due to their health-related effectiveness.

Figure 3. Role of Astaxanthin on WBC Index 10³ / mm³ in Carp

Chemical Composition of Fish Meat

Figure 4. There is no significant difference between all treatments in moisture content, it was 73%, 73.2%, 73.1%, and 73.1% for A, B, C, and D respectively. The results showed an increase in the protein, fat, and ash content were 18, 15, and 3% respectively, for fish fingerlings fed with astaxanthin at a rate of 0.15%. It is clear

from the results of the current study in Table 6. that the increase in protein, fat, and ash content was directly proportional to the increase in astaxanthin concentration. This is because astaxanthin contains a high percentage of carotenoids, beta-carotene, and lutein. These results are consistent with (Nakano, Tosa, & Takeuchi, 1995).

Figure 4. Chemical Composition of Fish Meat

Conclusion

From the analyses obtained in this study, we conclude that adding astaxanthin to fish feed improved the chemical components of fish meat and increased the value of the immune system in the fish in *C. carpio* when added at a concentration in 100 and 150 mg/kg.

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